

8T – The Fields Mixture

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Abstract:

By analyzing the setting of the 8T, and in particular the invariant multiplier of the primordial, i.e. the eight, author will argue that there is a mixture of fields of Bosons of different couplings. That is because the multiplier can be decomposed to a photon and a Boson of the weak interaction. Such an idea than creates a situation in which there are mixture of Bosons, or fields, another way to represent an interaction.

Introduction

The 8T is a the theory of variational curvature, the main equation (1) is describing the principle of equivalence between gravity and acceleration, and by demanding the two conditions $\partial g / \partial t = 0$ and $\frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$ we have the conditions to "dark energy" which Is the result of distinct manifolds interacting in areas of extremum curvatures, leading to an acceleration from those areas, and

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2.A)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.42) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

Now, suppose we would like to represent the invariant multiplier by a combination of Bosons.

$$8 = 5 + 3$$

$$8 = \gamma + \mathcal{W}$$

It is possible than to represent the multiplier by the following:

$$F_R \# = \left((\gamma + \mathcal{W}) * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V$$

Let the forth coupling and above be represented by the parameters:

$$N_{V4 \rightarrow V\infty} = \Lambda_k$$

$$K \rightarrow [4, \mathbb{R}]$$

$$\mathbb{R} \rightarrow \infty$$

So now it is possible to represent each coupling term in the following way, for the higher couplings as an example:

$$(\gamma + \mathcal{W}) \times \Lambda_k + 3 + \Lambda_k = \gamma\Lambda_k + \mathcal{W}\Lambda_k + 3 + \Lambda_k$$

$$\gamma\Lambda_k + \mathcal{W}\Lambda_k \tag{1.43}$$

equation (1.43) indicate that there is an interaction of the higher coupling terms, and therefore Bosons, with the electric and the weak interaction Bosons as each interaction contains elements from both. Since the invariant multiplier can be represented as a series of eight Gluons, the same applies there as well.

$$8 = 1 + 1 \dots$$

$$8 = \sum_{i=1}^{i=8} g_i$$

In other words, replacing the invariant multiplier by the prime combinations which represent it allows us another glimpse into the valuable interaction of the higher couplings. That is than a source of a prediction: The higher coupling terms are in constant interaction with the Bosons of the strong, weak and electric. If we represent each in terms of a diverging ripples of net curvature, than (1.43) indicate that there is a ripple intersection between those Bosons:

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t_n^2} N_V = \nabla^2 N_V$$

That is reasonable to assume as all of them are of the same class, the curvature class.

$$Q: Top \rightarrow Set$$

$$G_{class} = \{N_V | N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1)\}$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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